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NON-TRADITIONAL UNIVERSITY STUDENT OF TEACHING AS A (NON) TRADITIONAL READER

НЕТРАДИЦІЙНИЙ СТУДЕНТ-МАЙБУТНІЙ ВЧИТЕЛЬ ЯК (НЕ)ТРАДИЦІЙНИЙ ЧИТАЧ

У статті наведено приклади досліджень, пов'язаних з темою Я-концепції у нетрадиційних студентів університету як (не)традиційних читачів. У роботі акцентується увага на культурному, психологічному, педагогічному та здоров'я-збережувальному змісті мотивації та участі чеських, іноземних студентів, студентів з досвідом та без досвіду роботи на шляху до їхньої майбутньої педагогічної кар'єри. У статті викладено результати дослідження проявів (не)традиційних студентів-майбутніх вчителів як читачів (освітні напрямки, характеристика (не)традиційних студентів-майбутніх вчителів у Чеській Республіці, риси (не)традиційних читачів як студентів, фактори, що впливають на мотивацію чеських / іноземних студентів-майбутніх вчителів). Напівструктуровані інтерв'ю було проаналізовано за допомогою якісних методів.

Ключові слова: нетрадиційний студент, нетрадиційний читач, пропозиції щодо змін у педагогічній освіті, труднощі в навчанні та читанні.

The text introduces examples of studies dealing with the topic of self-concept of non-traditional university students in the role of (non) traditional readers. The paper points out the cultural, psychological, pedagogical, health contexts of motivation and participation of Czech, international, (non) intact students on the way to the future teaching career. It presents the results of a survey of the manifestations of (non) traditional university students of teaching as readers (educational paths, characteristics of (non) traditional students of teaching in the Czech Republic, features of (non) traditional readers in the role of students, factors influencing the motivation of Czech/international students of teaching). Semi-structured interviews were analysed using qualitative methods.

Keywords: non-traditional student, non-traditional reader, proposals for changes in teacher education, barriers to learning and reading.

Introduction. The Czech education system works mainly with external, quantitatively measurable, indicators of reading. Teachers across subjects should be interested not only in external factors that affect the level of their students' reading when working with a diverse range of texts but also in internal factors based

on students' motivation to read, their interests, behaviour, individual personalities, the extent of cognitive and emotional intelligence, etc.

The need to reinforce the curriculum and prepare university teaching studies for teaching methods of critical thinking, which help to solve various problem situations in everyday life,

strengthen in the current social trend. Developing the functional literacy of the population in today's digital world is a cardinal direction in which the university context is to develop systematically and comprehensively in connection with the outputs of lower levels of education and in conjunction with other forms of education, such as non-formal education or informal and lifelong learning.

The relation of traditional/non-traditional learning and traditional/non-traditional reading. The characteristics of (non) traditional university student's learning can be understood by many aspects, as well as his role to be perceived as a traditional or non-traditional reader. The current world welcomes and supports non-traditional university students in terms of place, time, means, content, a form of study, respecting individual advantages of disadvantaged students due to socio-economic status, health, individual students' plans because of sports representation at the top level, or the very successful artistic activity in the cultural world, etc. The official criteria for classifying university students as traditional and non-traditional can be understood very broadly, not only in connection with the educational system, but also with the everyday life and career of the individual, or their manifestations in reading.

Students from countries with lower economic status or students with severe disabilities come to Czech universities. However, unexpected changes also occur in the education context, when an initially healthy or successful student undergoes difficulties in everyday life and needs to accept personalised conditions of university study. A form of academic failure can also lead an individual to change from traditional to non-traditional study. It is still possible to perceive the disadvantage of gender predispositions in some of the field study profiles. On the other hand, more and more individuals are aware of the need for lifelong learning to increase their skills portfolio. It is a question of whether lifelong learning students can still be perceived as a non-traditional group of learners. However, there is a large group of students at a later age who expand their education for the desire for further knowledge or interest in a field of study that was previously unavailable to them for various reasons. A non-traditional student of teaching may have different or common educational, life, work goals based on everyday reality, needs, interest.

To recognise the reader's attitudes, the reflection of their interests, their motivation, the popularity of a specific genre, the type of text, the reader's background, their climate and environment, is necessary. The future teacher should be a role model for their students by

having a theoretical, practical and comprehensive overview of the characteristics of the reader at different ages, i.e. to lead students to the lifelong need for reading comprehension and for the lifelong need to learn.

Chaloupka (1982) describes and analyses the development of children's reading from the early childhood phase towards the older school age. As early as the end of the 1980s and 1990s, the emphasis was laid on research into children's reading, namely by describing, analysing and evaluating reading factors related to communication and reception, but also sociological, pedagogical and psychological aspects. The end of the 20th century and especially the rapid growth of IT in the 21st century brought a new perspective on the issue of reading. The world of interpersonal communication is shortening due to the fast amount of data transfer, regardless of the large territorial distance of the place where the individual participants in the communication are and transmit (receive, decode) communication signals.

V. Smetáček (1988), J. Tomana (1999), L. Lederbuchová (2004), R. Metelková, J. Svobodová, (2008), M. Švrčková (2011) and O. Zápotočná (2013) can be included among the significant researchers of the children literacy at the end of the 20th century and the turn of the 20th–21st century. Marhounová (1990), Homolová (2008), Hejsek (2015), Vicherková (2016, 2017, 2018) also dealt significantly with the problem of pubescent reading with a focus on reading interest and genre popularity. Velčovská (2019) also researched methods and organisational forms of teaching with a focus on communicative didactic games to develop reading strategies and learning strategies for pupils at the 2nd stage of primary school.

Reading Quality and Activity. Reading quality is related to reading activity, the individual's relationship to the information included in the text, their interest in various types of information sources, various types of texts, and the need to read and understand written information in terms of its content and form. The future pedagogue should understand that the quality of reading is significantly associated with the quantity of texts of different nature, i.e. across the field/professional focus. The level of learning and reading strategies is related to the level of critical thinking. Manifestations of reading competencies are closely related to the environment, the reading climate, reading patterns in the family, school, extracurricular activities, work and everyday contexts. The number of people with whom the content and meaning of written information are shared and communicated is an essential factor influencing the effectiveness of understanding

information from different communication spectrums. The importance of reading electronic and digital information through modern information technologies needs to be emphasised not only in the context of current COVID-19 pandemic. It is a question of the extent to which school/extracurricular institutions and pupils, parents, teachers, and the political public will withstand the growing expansion and dynamism of electronic and digitally mediated information towards current and future development in societal values. Reading and learning strategies, reading interest are related to reading habits. The reader's interest is based on several critical conditions, namely the amount of reading abilities and skills to read the text using a wide range of reading strategies leading to an understanding of written information according to the reader's traits, character and temperament. The essential condition for profiling the reader's interest is its dependence on the social and cultural context of the reader. Reading interest is influenced by many external and internal factors as well as by the quality of reading experience, reading perseverance and assertiveness, creativity, purposefulness.

In terms of reading attitudes, traditional and non-traditional readers in the Czech Republic can be classified following the research opinions of J. Trávníček (2017), who sorts Czech readers into four age groups, named explicitly as generations according to typical media of the given time. Trávníček (2017) classifies the reading generations into the following life cycles:

1. (15–24 years) – internet generation;
2. (25–44 years) – computer generation;
3. (45–64 years) – television generation;
4. (65+ years) – radio generation.

Working with different types of texts reflects in the categorisation of Trávníček's research concept (2017) a typical feature of the current and retrospective social atmosphere, a social context that is associated with the identity of individual generations of readers.

The Concept of Learning Process.

John Dollard and Neal E. Miller (1941) focused on the concept of the learning process and its components in relation to instinctual need, signal, response, and reinforcement such that «the learner must be driven to respond and rewarded for performing the response in the presence of the signal. The statement can express the fact that in order to learn, one must want something, notice something, do something, and gain something» (Dollard, Miller, 1941, p. 2).

Zounek (2009) defines the concept of learning as «a personal and social transformative act in the course of which a learner acquires new knowledge» (Zounek, 2009, p. 51).

The individual's ability to learn is influenced by several factors from a cognitive aspect. Learning and reading are complex processes influenced by creativity. Different personality traits affect the learning style. Mixed learning styles usually predominate. It is up to the teacher to respect the individual learning styles of the pupils, their individual potential related to learning. Learning styles are related to the level of social interaction and motivation, but also to the dominance of cerebral hemispheres in learning and reading processes. They are also related to pupils' learning and cultural context and the teaching context of the teacher. Mareš (1998) defined learning strategies as «larger-scale procedures by which a student implements a certain plan in a unique way in solving a given task, wants to achieve something and avoid something else» (Mareš, 1998, p. 58). Learning outcomes also affect the developmental stages and character features of the individual, as well as the motivational potential for learning, the choice of learning style and learning strategies. Learning from the text is an integral part of effective learning. By reading for knowledge and joy, we perceive, understand, analyse, remember different amounts of data, different quality of written information. Anne Mangen (in Wolf, 2020, p. 89) examined cognitive and emotional differences in reading between print and digital media and presented findings on superficial and incoherent eye movement «sliding on the surface» when reading from monitors and impaired reading orientation in digital text space. However, it is not clear enough whether this phenomenon affects the comprehension of the text.

Research Methodology and Background. The outputs from the conference in Sweden (1987) with the topic «Serving the Adult Learner – New Roles and Changing Relationships of Adult and Higher Education» are one of the research bases. They were processed as a national multiple case study of adults studying in different participating countries. «A summary of the development of adult education in Sweden from the extramural tradition at the turn of the century to the present-day university system has been added to Part I. Entitled» The Creation of Second Chance Routes for Adults: Origin Access and Quality «and Part II. «Patterns of Study Finance in Swedish Post Compulsory Education» (Abrahamsson, (Ed.), 1987). Out of the fifteen case studies, the topics related to the experience and observation of the lives of selected students in Sweden were inspiring for our research, specifically the paper «Some Figures and Comments on Study Assistance in Sweden» (Hansson, 1987 In Abrahamsson, 1987, pp. 59–64), and the text «Corporate Classrooms or Free

Academies? A Look at Future Adult Higher Education in Sweden» (Abrahamsson, 1987).

A partial starting point of our research survey is also the work of Souto – Otero, M., & Whitworth, A., 2017. «Adult participation in higher education and the «knowledge economy»: A cross-national analysis of patterns of delayed participation in HE across 15 European countries». Our interest laid in the cases of international students coming from disadvantaged socio-economic conditions and their socio-ethnic status. Studies by Gilardi, S. & Guglielmetti, C., (2011) track another group of students who can be considered at risk due to long-lasting disability.

In qualitatively oriented research, we focused on the issue of self-concept of traditional and non-traditional students concerning their role in the learning and reading process. The study (2020) presents the views of traditional and non-traditional university students of teaching at the Faculty of Education of the University of Ostrava in the Moravian-Silesian Region of the Czech Republic, focusing on selected cultural, psychological, pedagogical, health contexts of motivation and participation of Czech, international, intact and non-intact students on the way to the future career of a teacher. The research method was a semi-structured interview with selected students on a selected problem. Students' responses were literally transcribed, analysed and further processed by open coding (Švaříček & Šed'ová et al., 2007) and then categorised into profiles of characteristics of (non) traditional students, (non) traditional readers. Moreover, a form of self-reflection to identify whether selected respondents consider themselves traditional/non-traditional student, as well as traditional or non-traditional readers. Subsequently, students formulated the characteristics of a traditional/non-traditional student of teaching, traditional/non-traditional reader concerning the role of a student of teaching, motivational aspects of preparation for the teaching profession in Czech / international students. Subsequently, connections were created between the resulting codes and profiles of traditional/non-traditional teacher students, profiles of traditional/non-traditional readers for students of teaching, distinguishing factors influencing students' motivation for teachers' professional careers for Czech and international students studying in the Czech Republic. Semi-structured interviews with six university teachers of teaching were conducted in person in the classroom of the Faculty of Education of the University of Ostrava and also electronically via ZOOM and Skype (due to the government's decision to close universities in the Czech Republic with the

Covid-19 pandemic, February-March 2020). Some interviews with respondents were conducted repeatedly to clarify the more in-depth specification of the problem phenomenon. The intentional research sample consisted of five women and one man (students of teaching who are interested in teaching in future at technically oriented secondary schools). Students of science, technology and humanities were represented in the sample.

Description and analysis of semi-structured interviews with selected students of teaching. The following categorised codes were created in the course of interviews with selected students:

1. Characteristics of a traditional student of teaching: K1: regularity, formality, traditionality of study; K2: health; K3: language comprehension and financial adequacy

2. Characteristics of a non-traditional student of teaching: K4: permanent employment in the course of the study; K5: more self-study, lower number of hours of direct instruction, distant student; K6: parenthood and older age; K7: facilitation of learning; K8: self-reliance, faith in one's ability;

3. Characteristics of the traditional reader: K9: paper traditional texts, traditions of oral folk literature; K10: the joy of reading, free time, self-education by reading; K11: interest in professional reading from the library collection, professional growth through reading;

4. Characteristics of the non-traditional reader: K12: reader electronic and audio/digital context, means of information technology; K13: professional reading of scholarly and artistic literature in free time; K14: reading as a duty, a departure from the teaching profession;

5. The motivation for a teaching career in Czech students of teaching: K15: positive and comprehensive motivation for the teaching profession;

6. The motivation for a teaching career in international students of teaching: K16: ambition, positive and comprehensive motivation for the teaching profession; K17: purposefulness in the study and interest in innovative contribution in Czech educational practice, economic and political concerns about returning to the homeland, interest in permanent residence in the Czech Republic; K18: the motivational factor of study in the Czech Republic: field restrictions, unavailability of study in the home country.

The view of participating students on the features of a (non) traditional students of teaching, on the characteristics of a (non) traditional reader in the role of a future teacher, on factors influencing the motivation of Czech/international students of teaching

studies in the Czech Republic for their vocational training.

Question 1: In your opinion, who is a traditional university student of teaching (future teacher), what are their characteristics? Justify your opinion. Do you consider yourself a traditional student?

(K1: regularity, formality, traditionality of study) Pavla: «*They study full-time, commute to school regularly and perform tasks regularly. It's partly me, but only partly, because I also work part-time at an elementary art school near my home in a small town. I don't always attend the classes, but I try to complete 80%, or I agree on an alternative solution for fulfilling study obligations*». Markéta: «*They fulfil teachers' instructions and work mainly with traditional hardcover textbooks. Although I work partly, I consider myself a traditional student, I do everything regularly according to the rules*». Andrea: «*They write notes by hand, sometimes on a PC, learn from printed materials and resources, probably use electronic materials, because that is how most students work. I am a traditional student*». Denisa: «*Traditional student attends school in the full-time form of study, is adequately motivated to study, attends seminars, lectures, learns for exams, goes to libraries and study rooms. They are also someone with student status, i.e. they meet the form of attendance and age. I fulfil everything and thus I am a traditional student*». In accordance with the girls' opinions, the student draws attention to the aspect of health in relation to the fulfilment of study obligations. f(K2: health) Ota: «*They are a healthy student or one who do not have obstacles in attending school regularly and can study without restrictions. I am a non-traditional student*». The international student agreed with the views of other participating students but pointed out the problem of language comprehension and financial security throughout the studies (as well as Pavla and Markéta). (K3: language comprehension and sufficient funding for study) Nadja: «*It is probably a student who can speak and study in the language of the country without comprehension problems and without shortcomings with finances, who can fulfil study obligations according to the precise assignment, who attends the school regularly, obeys and follows the instructions of teachers and established valid school documents. I am an international student, but I study in the Czech language, so I am not a traditional student*».

Question 2: In your opinion, who is a non-traditional university student of teaching (future teacher), what are their characteristics? Justify your opinion. Are you a non-traditional student?

(K4: permanent employment in the course of the study), further (K5: more self-study, lower number of hours of direct instruction, distant student). For Petra and Dáša, a non-traditional student frequently combines study with full-time work, spends more time by self-study. Petra: «*A non-traditional student has a permanent job, they have to educate themselves in their free time (in order to better understand the curriculum), because they have fewer lectures at the faculty, they attend, for example, a distance learning*». Besides, Dáša defines the aspect of parenthood and older age (K6: parenthood and older age): Dáša: «*A non-traditional student is the one who, for example, combines their studies with non-temporary work, needs of a parent, studies remotely, for example at an older age*». For Marta, Anna, Ota and Nadja, a non-traditional student can also be assigned a desire to facilitate and speed up the learning process. (K7: facilitating and accelerating learning) Marta: «*And a non-traditional university student is a person who seeks facilitation, innovation and aids that lead to easier and faster learning, both in the form of various worksheets or a survey of diploma theses or e-books*». The other students agree. Anna: «*A non-traditional student does not need to take notes, they do not memorise the curriculum, and yet they master the curriculum*». Ota: «*A non-traditional student tries to get information about the curriculum from other (e.g. older) students and create their study portfolio, collect ideas from other students and also learn in the school hallway to save time and speed up the learning process*». Nadja also expresses her confidence in herself (K 8: self-reliance). Nadja: «*I am a non-traditional student, and that is why I think that I rely mainly on myself during my studies, I look for original ways of learning, mnemonic aids, I process questions for the exam independently. However, I'm pleased if someone also advises me, sometimes it shortens the learning time*».

Question 3: In your opinion, who is the traditional reader (in relation to students of teaching)? Are you a traditional reader?

Anna perceives the traditional reader in terms of preferring the reading of traditional texts, books in traditional paper text. Concerning the traditional reader, Marta recalls the readers of traditional collections of oral folklore, such as collections of songs in paper textbooks and illustrations of folk customs. (K9: paper traditional texts, traditions of oral folk literature). Anna: «*A traditional reader reads a paper book*». Marta: «*The term traditional makes me think of traditions that have been maintained and carried out before, when we may not have been in the world, such as the*

publication of songbooks, paper collections of texts and pictures on sayings etc. I don't care much about learning and reading practices of others; I'm quite a traditional reader. For individual, tradition is what they have been used to since they were a child. From generation to generation, traditions change, whether for bad or good, no one can say». Petra understands the traditional reader in terms of the popularity of spending free time reading and self-educating with reading, the joy of reading and with an overlap to the educational benefits. (K 10: the joy of reading, free time, self-education by reading). Petra: «*The traditional reader likes to read books in their free time, they are regularly interested in books, they like to educate themselves, they look for books about pedagogy, for example, I am a traditional reader*». The interest of reading not only in free time but also in the stage of professional teacher training can be attributed to the views of Dáša, who emphasises the reading of quality professional literature in paper text and also emphasises the reader's professional interest in attending educational institutions, such as libraries. (K 11: interest in professional reading from the library collection, professional growth through reading). Dáša: «*The traditional reader visits study rooms or libraries for proven sources full of the useful and necessary information, preferring quality scholarly (recommended) literature in paper form to internet sources. They are also interested in constant education in their field and read scholarly literature in their private life.*» Ota and Nadja also expressed their interest in reading professional books as a vital expression of the traditional reader. Ota: «*The traditional reader is like a steam locomotive, requiring constant fuelling to reach the destination station without obstacles, and therefore is interested in book news in the field*». Nadja: «*The traditional reader does not distinguish between free time and working time; they read for professional knowledge and joy*».

Question 4: In your opinion, who is a non-traditional reader (in relation to students of teaching)? Are you a non-traditional reader?

The non-traditional reader is characterised by various aspects. Anna, Ota, Dáša, Nadja also perceive non-traditional readers in connection with the use of various means of information technologies in an electronic and audio digital context. (K 12: reader electronic and audio/digital context, means of information technology). Anna: «*The non-traditional reader reads books in electronic form, listens to audiobooks.*» Ota: «*The non-traditional reader uses a wide range of non-traditional information technologies to read and learn*». Dáša: «*The non-traditional reader searches for*

resources in digital form. They use the Internet to search for information, download publications to a tablet, mobile phone or reader, which they perceive as convenient and comfortable, as they do not take up space and provide more information in one place.» Nadja inclines to the opinion that the non-traditional reader reads diverse literature in different ways in different environments and times. Nadja: «*The non-traditional reader reads anytime, anything, anywhere and in any way.*» (K13: professional reading of scholarly and artistic literature in free time). Marta characterised a non-traditional student by a description of her acquaintance, reads professional literature related to the teaching profession, both Czech and international, in his free time and is also interested in children's art literature, belles-lettres, and experiential literature. Marta: «*A friend from my hometown, who studies at the Faculty of Education of the University of Ostrava is a non-traditional reader. He differs from other friends with his way of thinking because he sees something more in teaching and therefore devotes his free time to professional teaching studies, reading international studies, children's art literature and experiential literature for children*». Petra formulates the problem of compulsory and optional non-traditional reading as a factor of possible escape from the teaching profession. (K14: reading as a duty, a departure from the teaching profession). Petra: «*The non-traditional reader reads only compulsory books to study, and therefore eventually may find that the profession of a teacher is not the right thing for them (they look for other ways to find a job in the labour market)*».

Question 5: What are the elements of motivation (cultural, pedagogical, psychological, health, etc. contexts) in relation to future teacher training (e.g. study and reading), namely for Czech students of teaching studying in the Czech Republic?

Czech students of teaching in the Czech Republic are positively motivated (they desire to complete their studies successfully and start teaching), they also have economic (financial) motivation (they perceive teaching as financial security), pedagogical-psychological motivation (they want to pass an adequate knowledge, skills, competence database of information across disciplines through a didactic way to pupils, they want to become good and innovative (creatively focused) teachers. (K 15: positive and comprehensive motivation for the teaching profession). Anna: «*Czech students of teaching are interested in gaining a good position at a good school, they also want to have a good salary, they are interested in passing on knowledge to the target group of*

students, they are interested in being a good teacher and bring new teaching methods to educational practice». Marta: «Czech students are motivated to prepare and implement the teaching profession: professional competence to educate the next generation, pass on knowledge and be a useful personality role model». Petra: «An interest in culture, interpersonal understanding and effective communication is typical in Czech students of teaching». Ota: «I think that student-teacher relationship is very important. A teacher's interest in their pupils, their interests, joys, problems, everyday life».

Question 6: What are the elements of motivation (in terms of cultural, pedagogical, psychological, health etc. contexts) in relation to future teacher training (e.g. study and reading), for international students of teaching in the Czech Republic?

International students are more ambitious in the implementation of their educational goals and have a positive, flexible and comprehensive motivation for the teaching profession not only in the Czech, but also in the European and global educational context. (K16: ambition, positive and comprehensive motivation for the teaching profession). Anna: «International students of teaching are ambitious and want to get a teaching position at a good school, get a good salary, be able to pass on knowledge to students, be a good teacher, bring new methods and knowledge in teaching to their home country. «Marta: «International students are motivated in the teaching profession by similar stimuli as Czech students, but they have a greater strike on goal. Above all, they have an aim to educate the next generation, to pass on knowledge and to be pedagogically useful in the Czech and foreign regions». Dáša: «They are motivated by a positive attitude towards youth and secure income». Furthermore, it is clear that students perceive other learning strategies for international students, which may be a factor of innovative changes in the Czech educational context (K17: purposefulness in the study and interest in innovative contribution in Czech educational practice, economic and political concerns about returning to the homeland, interest in permanent residence in the Czech Republic). Positive motivation for learning and professional orientation can also have a political and economic subtext for international students, in connection with anxiety and fear of returning home, sometimes at the cost of losing family ties in the country of origin. Nadja: «I would like to stay teaching in the Czech Republic after graduation because of peace and greater economic stability, but I do not know if I will succeed. As an international student, I do

my best to prepare for the profession. I want to be an excellent teacher and secure quality work and housing in the Czech Republic». Ota: «I think international students are more diligent and ambitious. They are interested in education, learning the local language, or assimilating into the local Czech pedagogical public, not returning home». In addition, Pavla mentions the motivation of international students to study fields that are unavailable abroad. (K18: the motivational factor of study in the Czech Republic: field restrictions, unavailability of study in the home country). Petra: «The fact that some fields cannot be studied abroad can be considered a strong stimulus to motivate international students to study teaching with a certain specialization in the Czech Republic».

Selected profiles of a (non) traditional student and a (non) traditional reader. Profiles of selected characteristics of students and readers introduce the attitudes of individual respondents in relation to understanding the roles of traditional and non-traditional student of teaching and their relationship to the concept of roles of traditional and non-traditional readers.

Results of qualitatively oriented research and interpretation of research data. The aim of the research was to describe, characterise a traditional/non-traditional student of teaching, traditional/non-traditional reader (in the role of a student of teaching), factors influencing the motivation of Czech/international students to prepare for the future profession from the perspective of teaching students studying at the Faculty of Education.

The key research results of this qualitative part of the study include:

1. Two out of six participating students consider themselves traditional students in the research survey, two students (studying concurrently with part-time work) consider themselves more traditional students, one international student considers herself a traditional and non-traditional student. She studies regularly and successfully as an international student she is frequently perceived as a non-traditional student in the Czech educational context, one student is considered a non-traditional student because of his severe disability and studies successfully with the help of an individual educational plan.

2. A common feature of the participating students is their interest in working as teachers of technically oriented secondary schools in the Moravian-Silesian Region across their diverse specialisation.

Table 1

Characteristics of a non-traditional student of teaching (K4, K5, K6, K7, K8)

Participating students of teaching	Self-concept of a non-traditional student/reader	Who is a non-traditional student/reader (according to students)
Anna	does not consider herself a non-traditional student	- no need to take notes; - does not memorize the curriculum yet masters it.
	does not consider herself a non-traditional reader	- reads books in electronic text; - listens to audiobooks.
Petra	considers herself a partially non-traditional student because of her part-time job at an elementary art school	- can have a permanent job while studying, can handle it; - has to educate themselves more in their free time; - has less direct instruction in distance learning.
	does not consider herself a non-traditional reader	- reads only compulsory literature to study; - is not very interested in the future teaching profession; looking for other job opportunities; - a little /a much searches for books with pedagogical overlap.
Marta	considers herself a partially non-traditional student because of her part-time job at an elementary art school	- seeks and uses innovative procedures and aids leading to facilitate, accelerate learning, is very creative.
	does not consider herself a non-traditional reader	- has different thought processes than the traditional; - sees a mission in teaching, he is interested in professional literature also in his free time; - reads international literature, studies, children's literature and adventure literature for children.
Dáša	does not consider herself a non-traditional student	- combines his learning successfully with work, - studies remotely; - is older (over 55 years old)).
	does not consider herself a non-traditional reader	- searches for sources of information in digital form; - downloads information to electronic and digital media (to save space and store more data in one place).
Ota	Considers himself a non-traditional student due to a severe disability	- tries to get key information about the curriculum from other students; - creates own study portfolio; - gathers ideas for study from various sources; - maximally utilises of time for learning (even during breaks, they learn, e.g. in the school corridor).
	does not consider himself a nontraditional reader	- uses a wide range of non-traditional information technologies and tools for reading and learning; - is ambitious, interested in book news in the field; - continuously educates.
Nadja	considers herself both traditional and non-traditional student because she studies regularly and successfully without any problems, but she is an international student studying in the Czech Republic	- relies on herself; - looks for original ways of learning; - processes the questions for the exam independently; - uses mnemonic teaching aids; - sometimes likes to get advice but decides for herself.
	considers herself a non-traditional reader, reads texts in four foreign languages	- reads diverse literature in different (even non-traditional) places and at every suitable occasion (in a suitable space-time), - reads for professional knowledge and for joy

3. Students who successfully fulfil their study obligations, study regularly (full-time), who are interested in the teaching profession and respect the teaching tradition are considered as traditional students of teaching.

4. Students with disabilities, students with an extraordinary creative focus, as well as international students studying in the Czech Republic, distant students, students with a permanent job in the course of their studies, students over the age of 55 are considered as non-traditional students of teaching.

5. Readers of classical literature reading traditional texts in paper text (sometimes even electronic texts) are considered to be traditional readers. They tend to visit libraries and study rooms, they do not distinguish between work and free time when reading, they have a desire to educate and self-educate by reading belles-lettres and scholarly literature, they belong to the group of motivated readers with an educational overlap.

6. Following readers are considered non-traditional readers in the role of future teachers:

- electronic textbooks and audiobook listener;

- reading books and study literature only out of duty;

- considering teaching as mission (interested in professional literature in their free time);

- reading international literature, studies, children's literature and adventure literature for children;

- searching for information and processing it in digital form and in electronic context;

- using a wide range of non-traditional information technologies and reading and learning resources;

- reading various texts for knowledge and joy in different time and space.

7. The key factors influencing Czech students' motivation include students' interest to effectively communicate comprehensive knowledge to the target group of students, to become a good teacher, the interest in modern (creative, activating) teaching methods and their transfer to educational practice, security in financial reward for work performed, interest in working with youth and being a role model for future generations, an aim to transfer professional and pedagogical-psychological theory into educational reality. The interest in culture, interpersonal understanding, effective communication, teacher's interest in their students, their interests, joys, problems, everyday life, respect for the teacher and mutual partnership also belong among the motivational factors.

Factors influencing international students' motivation in preparation for the future teaching profession include: interest in gaining a good and stable teaching position at a quality school

(in their home country and in the Czech Republic), motivation to change the concept of Czech education, or to understand it as a model for the concept of education in the home country, interest and motivation to study teaching with a positive attitude towards youth and security in financial evaluation, appreciation of Czech economic and political stability (peace), extraordinary interest and effort in study is frequently closely related to concerns returning to their home country with a lower economic and social status, their interest in assimilating into Czech society without language barriers, becoming part of the professional pedagogical public. Their interest in being independent, successful, purposeful, ambitious, with an effort to realise life dreams, namely, to live a better-quality life with an interest in Czech culture and literature, can be considered significant.

Conclusions and discussions. The sample showed that the factors influencing the level of reading and learning strategies in university students and their self-concept as traditional readers include working with a traditional textbook in paper text, which is consistent with the research findings of Fan & Kalley (1988) and their claim that textbooks are a factor influencing teachers' teaching strategies as well as pupils' learning strategies. An important finding is that traditional students of teaching are also considered traditional readers and that a student's study stay abroad is a factor that affects the student's identity in relation to the role of non-traditional reader (according to the participating student who is an international student and is also considered non-traditional reader).

Vašků's research (2019) dealt with electronic communication, its benefits and pitfalls in pedagogical reality, which pointed out the important task of the school in connection with the selection and use of selected means of electronic communication in relation to teacher-pupil, pupil-teacher communication. Motivational aspects are one of the key factors influencing the level of strategic learning and reading. The results of the research studies Cosman – Ross and Hiatt – Michael (2005), as well as the research of students of teaching Navarro & Soler (2014) also drew attention to the importance of motivating the university public to e-study. For international students, our research revealed certain motivational factors, signs of fear of returning to their homeland after graduation in the Czech Republic, which was also pointed out in McClelland (1984) in connection with the individual's efforts to cope with fears of failure. The research of Rabušicová, Rabušic, Šedřová (2008) pointed to an increase in motivation with the growing age of individuals who are more oriented to their position on the labour market than the generation of younger people.

The conducted qualitative research brought findings on factors influencing the motivation of students of teaching for the future teaching profession and pointed out the characteristics of traditional and non-traditional students of teaching in relation to traditional and non-traditional reading, a role of reader. The study also pointed out differences in socio-economic status of the students.

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